

MATRIX TOUGHENING AND ITS EFFECT

ON THE BEHAVIOUR OF CFRP

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Introduction

In the development of fibre composites, most attention has been concentrated on the behaviour of the material under stresses in the fibre directions. This behaviour is dominated by the properties of the fibres, and the properties of the matrices have tended to be regarded as of relatively minor importance. An example of fibre dominated behaviour is the tensile fatigue of unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) in which the excellent tensile fatigue behaviour of the fibres results in good tensile fatigue behaviour of the composite. In many practical uses of composites however, situations can occur in which dangerously high stresses may arise in the matrix and result in crack propagation parallel to the fibres in the matrix or fibre-matrix interface. Examples of matrix dominated behaviour are the rapid degradation which can occur during shear fatigue of CFRP (1), and ballistic impact damage due to the occurrence of high transient shear or transverse tensile stresses (2). In such situations the resistance of the composite to crack propagation parallel to the fibres is of considerable importance.

Like other composite properties, the resistance to crack propagation is highly anisotropic. For cracks propagating perpendicularly to the fibre, fracture energies (G_c) of CFRP range from a few kJm^{-2} for high modulus surface treated fibres to a few tens of kJm^{-2} for surface-untreated and high strength surface-treated fibres (3,4). In an ideal, perfectly aligned composite it seems probable that the resistance to crack propagation in a direction

parallel to fibres would be approximately equal to the resistance of the matrix material. Typically this is $\sim 0.15 \text{ kJm}^{-2}$ for the epoxide resins used in composites. In practice, because the fibres in CFRP are not perfectly aligned, there can be a contribution to G_C from the misaligned fibres through processes characteristic of a composite, such as pull-out or debonding, occurring in and around a tied zone at the crack tip. The tied zone is a region in which the crack has propagated through the matrix, but the opposite faces are still held together by fibres which are unbroken, or are broken but not pulled out. Experimentally it has been found (2) that a sharp crack may be introduced into a composite with a tied zone which is initially very small. When the crack is caused to extend, the tied zone can increase in length until it reaches some size determined by the fibre misalignment. Thus the fracture energy G_C may increase from a value similar to that of the matrix material to a much greater value as the crack propagates. This effect makes the definition and reproducible measurement of toughness more difficult than for a homogeneous material.

Since at least the initial growth of a crack in a direction parallel to the fibres is believed to be controlled by the toughness of the matrix, it is to be expected that the use of tougher resins would lead to an improvement in the matrix dominated properties controlled by this failure mode. There are a number of ways in which the toughness of an epoxide resin can be varied. Two methods are reported here. One, by the addition of liquid butadiene acrylonitrile copolymers, and the other by varying the resin:hardener ratio and thus the state of cure. The effect of the copolymer addition on a composite has been determined by measuring fracture energies for cracks propagating parallel to fibres. The effect of resin:hardener ratio has been studied rather more indirectly by observation of the torsional fatigue lifetime of the composite. In each case the composite system consisted of high modulus (Type I) surface-treated carbon fibres in an epoxide matrix.

Materials and Specimen Preparation

The epoxide resin used throughout was Ciba-Geigy MY750, an unplasticised diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A with a mean molecular weight of about 300 and an epoxide equivalent of 5.0 equiv/Kg. Two different curing agents were employed. For the torsional fatigue experiments in which the state of cure was varied, an anhydride curing agent, methyl nadic anhydride (MNA) accelerated by benzyl-dimethylamine (BDMA), was used. This system proved unsuitable for use with the rubber copolymer and instead an amine, piperidine, was used for that series of measurements.

It is well known that the toughness of epoxide resins can be enhanced by the addition of butadiene-acrylonitrile copolymers which precipitate in the resin as small spheres during curing (5).

Rubber precipitation is claimed to possess some advantages over other toughening mechanisms, such as the addition of a dissolved flexibiliser, as it results in toughening with relatively small decreases in resin rigidity, or glass transition temperature (6). Four samples of liquid carboxyl terminated butadiene-acrylonitrile copolymers (CTBN) with varied acrylonitrile contents were supplied by the B.F. Goodrich Chemical Company. The Goodrich company has observed that in a similar epoxide system to MY750 the rubber particle size decreases with increasing acrylonitrile content, so that with these samples a range of sizes could be obtained. Table I shows details of the CTBN rubbers.

Rubber toughened and untoughened resin plates were produced by casting into vertical moulds. The rubber toughened plates were prepared with a composition of 100 parts by weight (pbw) MY750 + 6 pbw piperidine + the appropriate weight of CTBN. The untoughened plates were prepared with a composition of 100 pbw of MY750 + 1 pbw BDMA + quantities of MNA between 60 and 90 pbw; and 100 pbw of MY750 + 6 pbw piperidine. The MY750:MNA:BDMA systems were degassed before casting or making composites, by placing in a vacuum chamber to prevent the entrapment of air bubbles. This procedure was not suitable for degassing a CTBN:MY750:piperidine mixture as it resulted in prolonged foaming. Instead, the mixture was warmed to reduce its viscosity and then after a few minutes either cast to produce a resin plate, or else used to manufacture composites. After curing, few bubbles were apparent to the naked eye. Curing of all the piperidine cured resins and composites was carried out at 120°C for 16 hours. The MNA cured materials were mainly cured at 120°C for 2 hours, but one of the systems, which contained 80 pbw of MNA, was postcured for 4 hours at 180°C and is referred to in the text as "well-cured".

Unidirectional composites were produced by a wet lay-up technique. The required quantity of fibres to make a 60 volume per cent composite was first soaked in warm resin, then gently squeezed to remove excess resin, and finally placed in a mould and pressed to stops.

For comparison, some measurements were also carried out on adhesive films which were produced by sandwiching resin between aluminium alloy adherends. The aluminium surfaces were prepared by immersion for 20 minutes at 61°C in a solution of 1600 ml water, 300 ml concentrated sulphuric acid and 100 gm chromium trioxide; followed by washing in water and drying at 62°C. These temperatures were recommended to avoid an alumina phase change at 67°C. The dry, prepared surfaces were then coated with the viscous, liquid resin and held together by clamps, the glue-line thickness, of 0.1 mm or 0.2 mm, being determined by metal spacers.

The Toughness of Cast Resins

Fracture energies of the cast resins were measured by compliance calibration techniques. The fracture energy (G_c) of a material, the energy required for a crack to propagate through unit area, is related to the load (P) at fracture and the variation of compliance (C) with crack area (A) by

$$G_c = \frac{P^2}{2} \frac{dC}{dA}$$

Experimentally, the procedure for measuring G_c consists of first calibrating the specimen by measuring the variation of compliance with crack length. G_c is then obtained from a similar specimen by measuring the load which causes the crack to propagate.

Two types of specimen were employed. For the rubber toughened resins, a contoured double cantilever beam (DCB) was used (7). During the course of the study, the simplicity and some other advantages of an alternative specimen, the double torsion (DT) type (8) became apparent and measurements on the untoughened resins were carried out with that. The two specimen types and loading arrangements are shown in Figures 1 and 2. It can be shown analytically and experimentally (7,8,9) that the compliance (loading point displacement divided by load) of each is related linearly to crack length. Provided G_c remains constant during the course of the experiment, crack propagation in specimens of these types should occur under constant load as shown in Figure 3, which depicts continuous crack propagation. Frequently this did not occur, instead the crack propagated intermittently in a stick-slip mode as shown in Figure 4. The two effects sometimes occurred in apparently identical materials. Where stick-slip behaviour occurs it is possible to define two fracture energies. A so-called initiation energy corresponding to the peak load, and a so-called arrest energy corresponding to the trough load. In this paper only the initiation energies are reported.

Figure 5 shows the variation of resin toughness with concentration of CTBN obtained using the tapered double cantilever specimen at a cross-head speed of 0.5 mm min^{-1} . Each point is the mean of several measurements made on each of three DCB specimens of a given composition. Since all three were obtained from a single plate the detailed variation of G_c which CTBN content may not be accurate. However, there is a clear trend of G_c tending to increase with CTBN concentration. The maximum mean value of 3.16 kJm^{-2} is an order of magnitude greater than the values measured by the DCB technique off the untoughened resins, which were $0.33 \pm 0.2 \text{ kJm}^{-2}$ for the piperidine cured NY750 and $0.16 \pm 0.01 \text{ kJm}^{-2}$ for the NY750: MNA:BDMA system. During stick-slip behaviour, the crack propagates rapidly causing a smooth surface and then slows down causing a rough region, finally arresting close to the start of the next

smooth region. Figure 6 shows these features on the surface of an untoughened resin. The rubber toughened resins displayed rougher fracture surfaces and Figure 7 is a high magnification optical micrograph of the equivalent of the smooth region. Whereas in an untoughened resin at that magnification the micrograph shows no features, there is a great deal of detail on the toughened resin fracture surface. Precipitated rubber particles can be seen in Figure 7, and Figure 8 is a high magnification scanning electron micrograph of a gold coated fracture surface showing a rubber particle in more detail. The sizes of particles have been estimated roughly from optical micrographs of polished sections and SEM photographs of fracture surfaces. Because the rubber spheres are distributed randomly in the matrix, a polished plane will show a range of circle diameters even if all the particles are of the same size. The particles are not all the same size and in order to compare the different materials Table II shows the diameter of a few of the largest of each. The table shows the results obtained both by optical microscopy of polished sections (P) and scanning electron microscopy of fracture surfaces (F).

Under certain circumstances specimens which exhibit a linear variation of compliance can be used to measure the variation of fracture energy with crack velocity in a relatively simple way. If a material which fractures in a continuous manner, as in Figure 3, is loaded rapidly to cause the crack to propagate and then the loading point displacement is held constant, the load relaxes as the crack continues to propagate until it decelerates and arrests. The inset in Figure 3 shows a typical relaxation obtained with a double torsion specimen in an Instron machine. Evans (9) has shown that the slope dP/dt of the relaxation curve can be directly related to crack velocity. A similar technique can also be used in stick-slip behaviour where the crack propagates in a not too uncontrolled manner. The inset in Figure 4 shows a load-time curve for a driven crack under those conditions. It has been shown elsewhere(10) that the slope of the unloading part of the curve (dP/dt) can be related to the crack velocity. Figure 9 shows the variation of G_c with crack velocity measured in this way from a series of MY750: MNA:BDMA resins with different states of cure.

Crack Propagation in Rubber Toughened CFRP

Three different compositions of rubber toughened resin were used to manufacture composites. They consisted of 9 weight per cent (w/o) of polymer C, and 3.2 w/o and 6.2 w/o of polymer B, thus representing three different sphere sizes. They were compared with composites of MY750:MNA:BDMA and MY750:piperidine.

The same carbon fibre tow was used to make all the composites. Because the strength and modulus of carbon fibres sometimes vary along the tow, these properties were measured by single filament tests on samples of tow taken immediately before and after the

length used to make each specimen. Table III shows this information for the fibres and Table IV shows the mean values of flexural strength, flexural modulus and interlaminar shear strength determined from each composite in three point bending. Span to depth ratios were respectively 16:1, 100:1 and 5:1, and the specimen cross-sections were 12.5 mm wide x 2.5 mm deep. The data are normalised to 60% and it can be seen that there are little or no significant differences in these conventional flexural properties between the composites at ambient temperatures.

For ease of fabrication, a parallel sided double cantilever beam (DCB) was used to measure the fracture energies of the composites. Six DCB CFRP specimens were made from each resin composition. From each set, two were selected and the compliance measured as a function of crack length for saw-cut cracks. Fracture energies were then obtained from the remaining four specimens. This was accomplished by introducing a crack with a jeweller's saw and sharpening it by pressing a razor blade into the crack tip; loading the specimen to cause the crack to propagate a short distance; unloading the specimen to obtain its compliance; relating the compliance through the compliance calibration to dC/dA ; and reloading the specimen to obtain the load at which the crack propagated again. Figure 10 shows the typical load-displacement curve for such an exercise. All fracture energy measurements were carried out in an Instron testing machine at a cross-head speed of 0.5 mm min^{-1} . During crack propagation a tied zone was created, as described in the Introduction, and the calculated fracture energies varied with crack length. Because the method of obtaining the compliance calibration used a saw-cut as a simulation of a crack, and thus did not take into account the effect of a tied zone on the compliance, the accuracy of the fracture energy measurements decreased as the crack grew.

Table V shows the mean initial fracture energies calculated from the loads at which a sharpened saw-cut began to grow, before the development of a tied zone. Each mean value is the average of between 6 and 9 measurements made on several different specimens. Figure 11 shows the typical increase in required fracture energy as a sharpened saw-cut crack grew and developed a tied zone. This data was obtained from one specimen containing 6.2% of polymer B. Here G_c is plotted against an effective crack length obtained from the compliance calibration, and, for reasons outlined above, the calculated fracture energy and crack length become less accurate as the tied zone grows. However, the increase of required fracture energy with increasing tied zone is clear. The microstructure of the rubber toughened composite is shown in Figure 12 which is an optical micrograph of a polished section. The presence of precipitated rubber spheres in the matrix can clearly be seen.

From Table V it can be seen that the initial fracture energies obtained from composites of untoughened resin are very similar to

the fracture energies of the resins themselves. However the initial fracture energies obtained from composites of toughened resin are considerably lower than those of the resins alone, and display only very modest increases in toughness over those of the untoughened resin composites. The similarity between the inter-laminar shear strengths of the toughened and untoughened composites suggests that the fibre-matrix interface is not significantly weakened by the presence of CTBN. The micrograph, Figure 12, shows that the presence of fibres does not prevent the precipitation of rubber spheres. Therefore clearly some mechanism is suppressing the toughening effect associated with the addition of the copolymer systems.

Resin Cure and Torsional Fatigue

The low frequency fatigue behaviour of unidirectional CFRP has been studied in torsion. Specimens consisted of rods 150 mm long by 6 mm square, which were machined down to a 6mm diameter round section along their centre 100 mm. One end was gripped in a rotatable chuck and the other was attached to one end of a moment arm. The other end of the moment arm was attached to a compression/tension load cell.

Figure 13 shows a set of data obtained on cycling at 0.1 Hz between fixed angular displacements $\pm\theta^{\circ}$. The applied torque initially decreases linearly with $\log N$ where N is the number of cycles. After a period there is a transition in behaviour when the torque decreases much more rapidly. Frequently the transition is accompanied by an audible cracking noise. Examination of polished sections, and radiographic techniques, have shown that before the transition there are no observable cracks in the material. After the transition there are clearly detectable cracks which run roughly parallel to the rod axis. Figure 14 is a micrograph of a polished section showing a crack running in the matrix and fibre-matrix interface.

Several different batches of composites have been made using resins with two different states of cure which in cast resins have resulted in significant differences in toughness. One of the resins had a composition MY750:MNA:BDMA of 100:70:1 and was cured for 2 hrs at 120°C, the other had a composition of 100:80:1 and was cured for 2 hrs at 120°C followed by a postcure of 4 hrs at 180°C. From Figure 9 it can be seen that they have very different toughnesses at the higher crack velocities which correspond to the fatigue work, since during fatigue a crack generally extends along a significant fraction of the length of a specimen in between 1 and 20 cycles, corresponding to crack velocities in excess of 5×10^{-4} m sec⁻¹.

Figure 15 shows the fatigue behaviour of the two different systems. Fatigue life has been plotted against maximum angular

displacement θ , in a fixed angular displacement series of measurements. Here fatigue life is defined as the number of cycles at which a macroscopic crack starts to propagate. It can be seen that there is no significant difference between the undercured and the well-cured systems.

Discussion

The obvious difference between the resin in a composite and the resin in bulk, is that in the former case it exists as a thin film, coating and joining the fibres. This film can be very thin, ranging from less than one μm to several μm . In order to examine whether the resin in thin film form possessed less toughness than in the bulk, the toughness of adhesive layers of the matrix systems were measured. This data was obtained by measuring the toughness of the bonds of adhesively joined aluminium cantilevers with a glue-line thickness of 0.2 mm, and is shown in Table V. All failed almost totally cohesively, and only the cohesive failure data is included in the table. Although the glue-line thickness at 200 μm is considerably greater than the resin film thickness in the composite, there has again been a suppression in toughness of the rubber toughened material compared with the cast state. Also, one adhesive bond was tested with a glue-line thickness of 100 μm . This contained 9% of polymer C and exhibited an energy of 1.18 kJm^{-2} which, when compared with a 200 μm glue-line toughness of 1.50 kJm^{-2} , supports the trend of decreasing toughness with decreasing film thickness for rubber toughened resins. There is no evidence of such a trend in the untoughened resins.

The mechanism by which the addition of a rubber precipitate toughens an epoxide resin is not well understood. At least three models can be hypothesised. These are:-

Rubber particle tearing - rubber spheres with intersect the crack plane can elongate and tear as the fracture faces open.

Localised crazing - in rubber modified thermoplastics it has been shown that the toughening effect of rubber results from the development of a great deal of crazing in the vicinity of the rubber spheres, under stress (11).

Plastic zone effects - a proportion of the copolymer may remain in solution and by plasticising the resin lead to a reduction in yield stress and a consequent increase in energy absorption due to plastic flow.

Of these, rubber particle tearing is an essentially local effect occurring only in the immediate vicinity of the crack plane, and is therefore not likely to be affected by film thickness. The other two effects could occur over the volume associated with the crack tip stress field and therefore would be affected by film thickness. There is little evidence in the literature of crazing

in cross-linked thermosetting materials such as epoxides. Consequently, to test the hypothesis of plasticisation of the matrix by dissolved copolymer, the yield stresses of the different, unreinforced resins were measured in compression. Table V compares the values for the different systems. For the untoughened epoxides, of which the fracture energy might be expected to be controlled by a yielding mechanism, the fracture energy is smaller for the higher yield stress as would be qualitatively expected. For the toughened resins there is however little or no significant variation of yield stress although the toughnesses vary considerably. This suggests that the increase in toughness by the addition of rubber is not due to plasticisation. McGarry (5) has attributed the rubber toughening of epoxides to a similar mechanism to that of rubber toughened thermoplastics, the generation of crazing in the vicinity of the inclusions. There is however very little evidence in the literature of crazing occurring in well-cured thermosets. Recently Lilley and Holloway (12) have published photographs of craze-like features in well-cured epoxides after stressing for considerable periods of time. Van der Boogaart (13) has reported seeing crazes around crack tips in an incompletely cured resin system very similar to MY750. It is possible that the addition of rubber prevents complete cross-linking in the vicinity of rubber particles and thus permits crazing, and the rough fracture surfaces as shown in Figure 7 may be caused by this effect. A detailed examination of this phenomenon has not been carried out.

There is a great deal of scatter in both the static and fatigue torsion experiments and it is not possible to detect any difference in the fatigue behaviour of the two systems. Interpretation of the torsional fatigue data has to be more speculative than that of the direct measurements of fracture energy by the double cantilever beam technique. Torsional fatigue is a rather more complicated phenomenon, and it is possible that the reasons for the similarity between the fatigue behaviour of composites with two different matrices are related to the conditions associated with the initiation of a crack, rather than its propagation. However the double cantilever beam measurements on the untoughened resin systems MY750:MNA:BDMA and MY750: piperidine, in Table V, also show that there is no measured difference in matrix toughness in the composite for resins which have very different toughnesses in the bulk. This, combined with the fatigue data suggests that the toughness of those relatively low toughness epoxides are masked by other effects in the composite.

Taken as a whole, the results presented here have shown that significant increases in the resistance to crack propagation parallel to fibres can be obtained by the use of very tough matrices, such as might be obtained by the use of rubber toughened epoxides. The increases in toughness obtained with rubber toughened matrices are not as great as would be expected from measurements on bulk resin because of a suppression of toughness

when the resin is in thin film form. No differences have been observed in toughness or torsional fatigue behaviour of composites by using conventional, untoughened resins of differing toughnesses, presumably because the effect of matrix toughness is masked by other effects in the composite at low levels of matrix toughness. Since the addition of CTBN copolymer does not appear to degrade the room temperature flexural and interlaminar shear properties of the composite, this method of toughening may prove useful in practice.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to W. H. McCausland and P. Venables for their assistance, and to P.R. Goggin for the measurement of single filament properties. Part of the work has been carried out under a contract from the Ministry of Defence (Procurement Executive).

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Table I

The CTBN Polymers

Polymer	Acrylonitrile Content (%)	EFHR*
A	UNKNOWN	UNKNOWN
B	24.2	0.054
C	28.0	0.047
D	18.0	0.054

*EFHR = equivalent per hundred parts of rubber

Table II

Microstructure of rubber toughened resins

P refers to polished sections, F to fracture surfaces

Largest Particle Diameter* (μm)

Polymer Conc. (wt%) Polymer Type	3.2	6.2	9.0
	A (P)	1.0	1.9
(F)	1.2	2.1	2.9
B (P)	0.6	1.2	1.5
(F)	0.8	1.1	
C (P)	0.5	0.5	1.5
(F)	0.8	0.9	1.6
D (P)	1.3	1.2	4.5
(F)	1.5	1.5	4.0

*Obtained by measuring a few of the largest

Table III

Carbon fibre data

Mean values of tensile strength and Young's Modulus

Uncertainties are: strength 3%; modulus 1%

Property Sample	Strength MNm ⁻²	Young's Modulus GNm ⁻²
Before C1	3020	424
Between C1 and C2	2961	451
" C2 " C3	2951	419
" C3 " C4	2829	417
" C4 " C5	2930	405
After C5	3182	404

Table IV

Mechanical properties of the composites, normalised to 60^v/o

Mean values are tabulated. Uncertainties are:

strength 5%; Young's modulus 3%; i.l.s.s. 3%

Composite	Composition	Strength MNm ⁻²	Young's Modulus GNm ⁻²	i.l.s.s.* MNm
C1	MY750/MMA/ BDMA	1038	184	67
		1111	198	67
C2	MY750/ Piperidine	1068	196	71
		1102	193	70
C3	3.2% B	1104	185	72
		1114	188	72
C4	6.2% B	1044	192	65
		1039	193	64
C5	9.0% C	1086	186	67
		1049	191	69

Uncertainties are standard errors of the mean

*i.l.s.s. = interlaminar shear strength

Table V

The initial fracture energies of the composites, the fracture energies of the adhesive films and bulk resins, and the yield stresses of the resin

Resin system	Fracture energies (kJm^{-2})			Yield stress of bulk resin (MNm^{-2})
	Bulk resin	Adhesive film*	Composite	
MY750/MNA/BDMA	0.16 \pm 0.01	0.14	0.24 \pm 0.02	63
MY750/Piperidine	0.33 \pm 0.02	0.28	0.28 \pm 0.03	45
MY750 + 3.2% B	1.40 \pm 1.10	0.33	0.37 \pm 0.03	43
MY750 + 6.2% B	2.20 \pm 0.20	1.35	0.36 \pm 0.04	43
MY750 + 9.0% C	3.20 \pm 0.30	1.50	0.49 \pm 0.07	41

*Uncertainties are $\sim 15\%$

Figure 1 Double Cantilever Specimen

Figure 2 Double Torsion Specimen

Figure 3 Load traces for continuous crack propagation and relaxation

Figure 4 Load traces for stick-slip crack propagation

Figure 5 Variation of resin toughness with CTBN

Figure 6 Fracture surface of untoughened resin

Figure 7 Micrograph of "smooth" region of fracture surface of rubber toughened resin

Figure 8 Scanning electron micrograph of rubber particle

Figure 9 The variation of fracture energy (G_c) with crack velocity (v) in MY750:MNA:BDMA

Figure 10 Load-displacement behaviour of a CFRP double cantilever beam

Figure 11 Variation of fracture energy during crack growth in CFRP

Figure 12 Microstructure of a rubber toughened composite

Figure 13 The decrease in torque during constant angular cycling of CFRP

